

Potential of functional analysis applied to Sentinel-2 time-series to assess relevant agronomic parameters at the within-field level in viticulture

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Abstract

Sentinel-2 satellite imagery offers a wealth of spectral information combined with a weekly temporal resolution. It is seen as a promising tool to extract spatial information about vineyards and link them to agronomic parameters. Usually, only one or a few images are commonly employed at specific stages like veraison in viticulture. Extracting further information from time-series images may be of interest; however, this remains an issue due to the noisy and complex nature of extracted time-series. The functional analysis proposes a robust continuous representation of these time-series, which can then be used with adapted statistical tools. This paper focuses on extracting relevant information at the within-field level on two vineyards in Spain, which can be jointly interpreted with field observations and measurements. More precisely, it discusses the use of popular linear dimensionality reduction techniques, namely Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Partial Least Square (PLS), adapted to functional data in order to decompose NDVI time-series into a weighted sum of several functional components. The unsupervised methods, like PCA, decomposed the spatial structure within the vineyards using a few components, resulting in a better and more manageable dataset than the one obtained using simple non-constrained methods. The results show significant correlations with ground-truth data showing the added value of considering the whole NDVI temporal series compared to a single NDVI map at veraison. The proposed approach provided helpful information about each component's yearly trend. Moreover, the results are linked to grapevines' seasonal phenology and management practices, highlighting phenomena affecting

33 the vineyard's development. This method is particularly suited for interactions with field
34 experts, who may derive relevant agronomic information from the decomposition maps.

35

36 Keywords: PCA, Vineyard, Dimensionality reduction, functional analysis, clustering.

37

38 Introduction

39 Satellite imagery is widely used in vineyard studies because it is related to vegetation (Vélez *et*
40 *al.*, 2020). It can be applied to the analysis of within-field variability of the water status of the
41 soil and plants (Borgogno-Mondino *et al.*, 2018), harvest prediction (Sun *et al.*, 2017), the
42 analysis of the spatial heterogeneity of evapotranspiration (Knipper *et al.*, 2019) or the
43 classification of vine fields according to their vigor level (Di Gennaro *et al.*, 2019). Compared
44 to satellites, UAVs are also an interesting source of information because they offer higher
45 resolution and more acquisition flexibility; however, UAVs have several disadvantages, such
46 as having a smaller swath. In any case, UAVs offer a different and complementary profile to
47 satellites (Emilien *et al.*, 2021). In this respect, the Sentinel-2 satellites (European Space
48 Agency's Copernicus project) are balanced in their spatial resolutions (10-60m), providing high
49 temporal resolution data and can be particularly helpful due to the free nature of the images and
50 the relative ease of access (<https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>). The consequence is that although
51 Sentinel-2 data have lower spatial resolution than typical UAV imagery, it is known to be able
52 to detect relevant spatial variability within the vineyard in the absence of inter-row grass and if
53 individual vine management is not the goal (Sozzi *et al.*, 2020; Di Gennaro *et al.*, 2019).
54 Moreover, according to ESA (2015), these satellites provide spectral information in multiple
55 bands that allow computing many vegetation indices, which are of great interest for agricultural
56 applications and, in particular, the six bands covering the red/red-edge spectral interval from
57 650nm to 900nm that allow computation of the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
58 (NDVI; Rouse *et al.*, 1973). It has been shown that NDVI images at the veraison stage were the
59 most relevant to assess parameters related to the vine vigor and resulting harvest quality
60 (Anastasiou *et al.*, 2018; Vélez *et al.*, 2019).

61 The availability of time-series makes it possible to consider all the images acquired during the
62 vegetative period and not to be limited to an image at a single stage. Devaux *et al.* (2019) have
63 shown, using Sentinel-2 images, that the whole temporal NDVI series over the growing season
64 may bring relevant information on the field and its spatial variability (for instance, blocks with

65 different management units and vegetative developments). However, it is difficult to analyze
66 the potential relationship with relevant agronomic parameters considering all the available
67 Sentinel-2 dates due to the temporal data's high dimension. Moreover, it is usually highly
68 correlated and non-continuous (defined by satellite acquisition dates).

69 Functional analysis (Ramsay *et al.*, 2005) has been proposed to address these issues by
70 summarizing the whole curve shape of non-continuous measured data. It aims at proposing a
71 continuous and smooth representation of the data that small local curves or functions can model.
72 While that representation may make the data theoretically infinitely dimensional, it can
73 effectively consider different temporal dynamics at different scales while being relatively
74 robust to noise (Febrero-Bande *et al.*, 2008). Functional representation can arise naturally in
75 research domains such as spectroscopy, in which near-continuous data is already available.
76 Recent advances have increased the use of functional data for outlier removal (Febrero-Bande
77 *et al.*, 2008), regression (Goldsmith *et al.*, 2011), or classification (Leng *et al.*, 2005).
78 Functional data can also be easily derived to describe slopes and locate inflection points. This
79 paper will focus on its use to extract relevant information from NDVI time-series at the within-
80 field level, which can be jointly interpreted with field observations and measurements. More
81 precisely, it focuses on using popular linear dimensionality reduction techniques, Principal
82 Component Analysis (PCA) and Partial Least Square (PLS), applied to functional data to
83 decompose NDVI curves into a weighted sum of several components. That decomposition can
84 then be used to create several complementary maps describing different spatial dynamics in the
85 vineyard.

86 Based on a real case study in viticulture, the objectives of the paper are, therefore: i) to test the
87 interest of considering the whole NDVI time-series to estimate agronomic parameters of interest
88 at the within-field level, ii) to show how classical multivariate analysis methods (dimension
89 reduction) based on functional analysis are relevant to account for inter-image noise
90 management and agronomic variables estimation simultaneously, and iii) finally to discuss the
91 applicability of the approach by considering a real application.

92 **Materials and Methods**

93 **1. Vineyards**

94 The experiment was carried out during the 2018 campaign, using two datasets taken from two
95 commercial vineyards, one in 'Villanueva de Duero, Valladolid' (Vineyard A), planted in 2003,
96 and the other one in 'Aranda de Duero, Burgos' (Vineyard B), both in Spain (Table 1). They

117 2. Ground-truth data

118 A grid of equally distributed sampling sites (SS) was established in each vineyard: 16 SS in
119 vineyard A and 98 SS in vineyard B (Figure 1). For vineyard A, a SS corresponded to 10 vine
120 plants (five in one row and the other five in the adjacent one), resulting in 160 sampled vines.
121 In vineyard B, a SS corresponded to 3 vines (along the row), resulting in 294 sampled vines.
122 Each SS included fewer plants in vineyard B since it is a larger vineyard, and the priority of
123 sampling was to cover the whole area during a single sampling campaign.

124 Each SS was georeferenced with a Triumph-2 (Javad, USA) RTK receiver connected via
125 Bluetooth to an Android smartphone to access local RTK correction signals.

126

127

128 *Figure 1 - Sample sites and irrigation sectors of (left) vineyard A and (right) vineyard B.*

129 The vineyards belong to a more significant project in which several parameters related to
130 agronomic, abiotic, orographic, and harvest quality variables were monitored. In order to ease
131 the comparison, the variables were interpolated using kriging (equation 1) after the semi-
132 variogram was fitted to the observed semi-variance (Figure 2):

133
$$\hat{z}(x_0) = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i z(x_i) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

134 where \hat{z} is the estimated value at point x_0 , λ_i are the weights, and z are the known values at
135 points x_i . The measurement of these parameters was carried out following standard protocols in
136 viticulture which will not be described in this paper. Instead, the reader can refer to Hidalgo
137 (2006), Reynolds (2010), and Jackson (2020) for a detailed description. Note that all
138 measurements performed at the plant level were assigned to the geographic coordinate of the
139 Sampling Site. Regarding agronomic variables, five parameters were evaluated: pruning wood
140 weight (PWW), yield at harvest (Yield), and average cluster weight (CW). Moreover, the

141 grapes' typical quality parameters were measured: Brix, Sugar, pH, total acidity, malic acid,
142 tartaric acid, and potassium. Additionally, several abiotic and orographic parameters were
143 measured at each SS, such as soil texture (sand, clay, and silt), soil electrical apparent
144 conductivity (σ), pH, elevation, organic matter (OM), and Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC). In
145 order to simplify the analysis, only a few variables were selected: Pruning wood weight (PWW),
146 Yield at harvest, Cluster weight (CW), Tartaric Acid (TA), soil fraction in Clay, Sand and Silt,
147 soil Organic Matter (OM), soil Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC), and Soil electrical apparent
148 conductivity (σ), aiming to include the most relevant agronomic and abiotic parameters for
149 vineyard managers in viticulture (Keller, 2015).

150

151

152 *Figure 2 – Example of kriged maps on vineyard A (first two figures) and vineyard B (last two figures).*

153 An additional specific variable was considered for vineyard B, which presented specific within-
154 field spatial patterns (Figure 3), probably explained by a higher organic matter level
155 (Vodyanitskii and Savichev, 2017) or ephemeral streams, causing sediment transport or even
156 erosion (White, 2015). The ephemeral streams hypothesis is more likely since it fits with the
157 vineyard's elevation map, which is lower on the southwest side, causing streams to flow towards
158 the river.

159 This peculiarity was present only in vineyard B and was considered a driver that may explain
160 plant vigor differences due to changes in soil properties and water content (Yang *et al.*, 2019).

161
162 *Figure 3 – Soil specificities of Vineyard B, map of "ephemeral streams and possible higher concentration in organic matter"*
163 *corresponding to darker patterns highlighted in dark blue from a visible image in winter (left) and elevation map (right)*

164

165 3. Satellite data acquisition and processing

166 Sentinel 2 Level-2A imagery was downloaded, and cloudy dates were manually removed.
167 Images were used to build time-series, the vineyard boundaries were cropped, and the NDVI
168 was computed for each pixel over time. B8 and B4 Sentinel-2 bands were used to compute the
169 NDVI following equation 2. Obvious outliers were removed from the analysis; they included
170 paths in vineyard A. No pixels were removed in the vineyard B.

$$171 \quad NDVI = \frac{(NIR-red)}{(NIR+)} = \frac{(B8-B4)}{(B8+B4)} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

172 For the analysis, the 2018 NDVI time-series were limited from April to September. Figure 4
173 shows raw NDVI curves on each vineyard for each pixel.

174
175 *Figure 4 - NDVI evolution during the year 2018 for pixels in vineyard A (left) and vineyard B (right). The red curve indicates the*
176 *mean NDVI evolution in each vineyard.*

177 4. Functional representation and dimensionality reduction

178 The raw discrete time series were then transformed using functional analysis (Jolliffe, 2002).
179 Given the original discrete data X (each point is an NDVI value derived from Sentinel-2
180 images), a functional representation Y of the data aims to create a smoothed continuous

181 representation of that data, meaning the functional data does not exactly fit the original discrete
182 data points. Residuals can be computed in a similar way to classical regression problems
183 (Equation 3)

$$184 \quad Y_i(t) = X_i(t) + \varepsilon_i(t) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

185 where $\varepsilon_i(t)$ are the residuals not explained by the functional representation, i is a sample (time-
186 series for a given pixel), and t is the time. Residuals may be related to noise or punctual
187 phenomena not accounted by the functional data.

188 A non-parametric approach (Ferraty *et al.*, 2006) was chosen to obtain the data's functional
189 representation. It uses a Gaussian smoothing kernel and a bandwidth parameter w (Equation 4).

$$190 \quad M_{ab} = \frac{1}{w} K\left(\frac{t_a - t_b}{w}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

191 The matrix M , whose elements are the weights between points (a and b are the matrix rows and
192 columns) in the time series, can then be employed to compute the smoothed data (Equation 5).

$$193 \quad Y = M.X \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

194 This approach was preferred over the parametric approach, as proposed by Ramsay *et al.*,
195 (2005) because it is easier to settle and interpret as it involves only a kernel choice with a
196 bandwidth parameter. The higher the bandwidth, the higher the smoothing and the higher
197 residuals are, with a possible loss of information. Figure 5 exemplifies the effect of three
198 different kernels, corresponding to three different bandwidths, on the NDVI time-series of
199 vineyard A. In a first approach, a $W = 5$ was chosen to mitigate the smoothing vs. a potential
200 loss of information.

201
202 *Figure 5 - Effect of the bandwidth w on non-parametric functional analysis representation of the vineyard A data. (a) NDVI*
203 *curves for all the pixels (grey lines) within the vineyard (b) Example of NDVI curve for one pixel (blue line) with original*
204 *Sentinel-2 measurements (black dots) and confidence envelope (red dotted line) overlaid.*

205 The next step involves reducing the dimensionality of the time series, going from high
206 dimensions to a handful of informative components related to spatial phenomena in the

207 vineyard. Dimensionality reduction aims at doing this in an unsupervised (no training samples
208 available) or a supervised way (training samples, e.g., yield measurements available).
209 Several methods exist for seasonality decomposition and summarizing temporal information in
210 time series, such as ARIMA (Box *et al.*, 2015) or exponential smoothing models (ETS,
211 Hyndman *et al.*, 2008). In this paper, a Functional Principal Component Analysis (f-PCA,
212 Cardot *et al.*, 1999), which is the direct adaptation of PCA to functional data, was chosen. The
213 main goal of f-PCA is bringing classical component decomposition (PCA) to semi-continuous
214 time series. It was preferred over other methods for several reasons: i) the study was conducted
215 on a single year, meaning no cyclical patterns need to be extracted, only a main trend during
216 the summer season ii) scores and components generated by the PCA decomposition have a
217 natural interpretation and can be used to produced visual maps iii) the functional paradigm
218 combined with non-parametric dimensionality reduction allows us to handle Sentinel-2 related
219 noise efficiently. With the f-PCA, each sample (NDVI evolution throughout the year for a pixel)
220 can be expressed as a set of scores for each principal component following Equation 6.

$$C_i(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K S_{ik} \xi_k \text{ Eq. 6}$$

221 where S_{ik} is the score of sample i for the principal component k and ξ_k is the principal
222 component function which can be itself expressed as a set of functional basis. The choice of the
223 number of components depends on the explained variance (like for classical PCA).
224

225 Functional Partial Least Square (f-PLS) (Preda *et al.*, 2007) was chosen as a complementary
226 supervised method for the study to take advantage of the availability of a scalar variable (such
227 as field measurements). f-PLS was performed to consider a subspace maximizing the
228 covariance between the exploratory variables (functional data) and available ground truth data.
229 In other words, f-PLS projects the data in a way that classical regression can be easily
230 performed. The need for a scalar explanation variable means not every pixel can be used to train
231 the model, which can be a problem for vineyard A with few measurement sites.

232 Figure 6 presents a decomposition example of a set of NDVI curves into 3 Principal
233 Components (PC) curves (interpretation would be similar for f-PLS Latent Variables). The
234 individual curves for each sample can themselves be decomposed as the PC weighted by the
235 sample score, indicating how a trend modeled by a component is modulated for each pixel in
236 the vineyard. Time-series can then be summarized by a set of scores (equal to the number of
237 principal components) that best describe the whole original time series. Since the samples are
238 pixels, it is possible to create a score map for each PC. In Figure 6, the bottom row is a
239 representation of the reconstructed curves using the principal components and the scores. For

240 example, the PC1+2+3 reconstruction is a sum of the first three components weighted by the
241 pixel scores. These reconstructions can be directly compared with the original signal in order
242 to obtain residuals time-series. Unlike the global scores, which summarize the whole time
243 series, residuals can be mapped at any date, being helpful to check specific dates that are poorly
244 modeled by the decomposition. Further results were analyzed using the component curves, the
245 global score maps, and the residuals maps.

246
247 *Figure 6 - Visual decomposition of NDVI curves as a weighted sum of the 3 functional principal components (columns). Top*
248 *row represents the components modulated by the scores. Bottom row represents the time-series reconstruction using different*
249 *combinations of components. The red curves detail the decomposition of an example time-series (pixel within the vineyard).*

250 5. Validation

251 Spearman correlation analysis was used to check whether the components obtained from the
252 dimensionality reduction are linked to measured variables in the vineyard. Since measurements
253 are punctual, only the data at these Sample Sites was considered. Additionally, a Mann-Whitney
254 test was used to test for significance on categorical variables in vineyard B (stream zones/non-
255 stream zones and organic/non-organic management zones). This statistic considers the number
256 of samples used and thus may be adapted to low sample sizes.

257 Subsequently, functional representation and associated dimensionality reduction algorithms
258 were explored on vineyards A and B in order to assess if they can explain known spatial
259 variabilities within the vineyard (due to various factors such as soil, water status, or
260 management practices) better than conventional veraison maps. The study first focused on

261 applying f-PCA and later on a comparison of the results using f-PCA and f-PLS. Field data
262 presented beforehand were used to validate these observations.

263 All image, processing, and data analyses were performed using QGIS (version 3.14.X, QGIS
264 developer team 2020) and customized codes written in R statistical program (version 4.0.3, R
265 Foundation for Statistical Computing (R Core Team 2019), <https://www.R-project.org/>,
266 Vienna, Austria) using 'fda.usc' package as the basis for functional analysis representation
267 (Febrero-Bande *et al.*, 2012), among others such as 'raster', 'sf', 'sp', 'rgdal' and 'rgeos'.

268 Results

269 4.1. Previous exploratory analysis

270 A first exploratory data analysis on yield and Pruning Wood Weight (PWW) confirms that
271 vineyard A has much less variability than vineyard B; it also has fewer measurement sites since
272 it is a smaller vineyard. Figure 7 highlights the differences in the magnitude of variation in yield
273 and PWW for both vineyards. Upon conducting simple regression, it appears PWW has the best
274 correlation with the Sentinel-2 NDVI at veraison, confirming many literature studies on the
275 ability of NDVI at veraison to estimate vegetative plant biomass and plant vigor.

276
277 *Figure 7 - Classical maximum likelihood regression between NDVI at veraison (July 31 Sentinel-2 image was used) and*
278 *yield/Pruned weight on vineyards A and B. Vertical lines, dot color, and size indicate fit residuals. Associated r values*
279 *(Spearman correlation) are indicated in the bottom right corner of each plot.*

280 However, these studies only focus on NDVI information at one date and do not use the available
281 temporal information. The functional analysis combined with dimensionality reduction aims to
282 use this information to perform a general decomposition of seasonal time-series and could
283 potentially be a relevant link to field values.

284 4.2. Spatial structure of f-PCA components

285 Only the first three principal components, accounting for more than 95% of the variance on
286 both vineyards, are considered in the study. Figure 8 presents the score maps for each
287 component. These scores, computed on the whole time-series, are compared to NDVI maps at
288 veraison for both vineyards A and B. While NDVI and component scores do not share the same
289 scale, these values' global spatial organization within the vineyard can be compared.

290 (A)

291 (B)

292 *Figure 8 - Comparison between classical veraison NDVI map and the first three components of PCA in both vineyards. (A)*
293 *Vineyard A and (B) vineyard B.*

294 Results show that the first principal component map tends to be very similar to the NDVI map
295 obtained at veraison; both maps highlight the same spatial patterns. According to the
296 correlations between the first component and field values shown in table 3, the first component
297 is linked to the final pruning wood weight. Moreover, the correlation is higher between the
298 PWW and the PC1 ($r = -0.62$ and -0.51 , respectively for vineyards A and B) than just the PWW
299 and the veraison map ($r = 0.54$ and 0.39 , respectively for vineyard A and B. Figure 7).

300 The first principal component is also linked to other quantitative parameters such as the yield,
301 cluster weight, and tartaric acid in vineyard A, but only with tartaric acid in vineyard B.

302 Additionally, strong correlations were found significant with soil variables such as sand and silt
 303 content, Cation Exchange Capacity, organic matter content, and soil apparent electrical
 304 conductivity. Detailed agronomic analysis of the relationships between the variables is beyond
 305 the scope of this paper; however, the results highlighted here are consistent with other literature
 306 results, showing that vine vigor is often related to soil characteristics. These characteristics
 307 directly determine other parameters such as access to water or soil fertility and indirectly the
 308 components of yield and grape quality, i.e., the significant correlation with tartaric acid may be
 309 related to the total vegetation (Hidalgo, 2006). It seems that the first principal component of the
 310 f-PCA integrates the changes in NDVI over the entire vegetative period with sites that
 311 systematically have high NDVI values and sites that systematically have low NDVI values. The
 312 NDVI image at veraison after plant vines stopped growing is somewhat the final result of the
 313 plant growth, explaining the remarkable similarity between the first component and the map at
 314 veraison. This result confirms the relevance of the f-PCA. However, the other components must
 315 be analyzed in order to investigate their additional potential information.

316 *Table 3. Vineyard correlations (Spearman). Significance level: * p-value<0.05; ** p-value<0.01.*

Vineyard	PWW (kg)		Yield (kg)		CW (g)		TA (g/l)		Clay (%)	
	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
PC1	-0.62**	-0.51**	-0.36**	-0.16	-0.48**	-0.19	-0.74**	-0.36**	-0.46	-0.24
PC2	-0.09	-0.08	0.15	0.39**	0.12	0.53**	-0.44	0.05	-0.75**	0.06
PC3	0.12	-0.14	0.35**	-0.15	0.36**	-0.02	0.22	-0.02	-0.05	0.12
Vineyard	Sand (%)		Silt (%)		OM (%)		CEC (meqNa/100g)		σ (uS/cm)	
	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
PC1	0.68**	0.54*	-0.63**	-0.54*	-0.73**	-0.48	-0.66**	-0.47	-0.48	-0.54*
PC2	0.69**	0	0.14	-0.01	-0.36	-0.15	-0.81**	-0.22	-0.7**	-0.41
PC3	-0.15	0.06	0.38	-0.09	0.28	-0.12	0.13	-0.17	-0.24	0.02

317
 318 The correlations between the second component of each vineyard and the vineyard variables
 319 differ. In vineyard A, it is consistent with soil variables such as clay and sand content, soil
 320 apparent conductivity, and Cation Exchange Capacity, showing clear zones that deviate from
 321 the main vigor (growth) trend highlighted by the first component and related to soil variations.
 322 However, in vineyard B, the second component is more correlated with the plant variables than
 323 the veraison map showing that the correlation between the yield and the PC2 is higher ($r = 0.39$)
 324 than the correlation between the yield and the veraison map ($r = 0.23$, Figure 7). Furthermore,
 325 the second component of vineyard B divides the vineyard into two sections: the western part
 326 with the lowest scores and the eastern part with the highest scores. These two sections were not

327 visible either in the veraison map or the first component map. They fit with different clones and
328 different management practices (Figure 1).

329 The interpretation of the third component should be handled with care since it explains less than
330 5% of the total variance. It may indicate some remaining border effects and subtle heterogeneity
331 within the zones that were not explained by the first and the second component. It is not strongly
332 related to any soil components but to cluster weight and yield variables. One hypothesis would
333 be that the third component accounts for residual variation in vigor explained by the different
334 source-sink ratios between yield and canopy development (Urretavizcaya *et al.*, 2017).

335 The three components exhibit clear spatial patterns, with different zones cohesive with field
336 observations. Unsurprisingly, additional components led to more noisy maps, supporting the
337 decision only to use a handful of components.

338 4.3. Assessment of principal components functions

339 Plotting the functions defining the principal components can be viewed as a complementary
340 analysis (Figure 9). The results are based on the example of vineyard A, knowing that Vineyard
341 B presents the same characteristics. Although this visualization of principal component
342 functions loses relevant spatial information (pixel scores within vineyards), it provides a general
343 temporal description of the phenomena modeled.

344 The first gained insight is that June and the resulting spatial heterogeneity cannot be modeled
345 with a single component since each component exhibits different variation patterns. The first
346 component models the vineyard's primary trend (also valid for vineyard B) over the whole
347 vegetative growth, confirming the assumption of integrating the vigor's changes over the entire
348 vegetative period. As a result, the first component models the general trend of the vineyard
349 (Figure 9 left), and the scores, as explained in figure 6 and shown in figure 9 right, represent
350 the deviation of each within-field site from this general trend. Figure 9 right also confirms the
351 similarity between NDVI values at veraison and scores of the first component. In terms of
352 temporal variation, it should be highlighted that the first component experiences a slight
353 depression at the beginning of July, which modifies the upward trend and matches with the
354 summer pruning operation.

355 The adjustments applied by the other components have different amplitudes depending on the
356 date. The second component firmly adjusts the representation at the beginning of June, while
357 the third component adjusts the representation in June and August (firstly in a positive and
358 secondly in a negative trend). The importance of June may be linked to the complex dynamics
359 within the vineyard at this time. Indeed, the vine growth is at its maximum and starts to decrease

360 before entering the plateau zone. Some factors may have a significant impact on NDVI values
361 during this period. The correlation with soil parameters indicates that the specific soil conditions
362 (such as water availability or soil fertility) may affect NDVI changes (and therefore vine
363 growth) and may explain precocity or delay in growth stop. Finally, note that all components
364 exhibit a decrease in absolute value at the beginning of July. This result may be related to the
365 previously mentioned summer pruning period, which homogenizes the size of the canopy and
366 the resulting observed NDVI over the whole field. The f-PCA shows here that this period has a
367 low informative value due to canopy management operations.

368
369 *Figure 9 - (left) "Centered principal functions" obtained for the first three components of PCA on vineyard A. (right) NDVI*
370 *functional data*

371 4.4. Mapping of unexplained variance

372 Figure 10 presents maps of residuals at four critical dates during the season for both vineyards.
373 It was computed by considering the difference between the reconstructed and the original NDVI
374 values at a given date. Since residuals can be computed at any date, the main advantage is
375 getting a more precise temporal interpretation of the f-PCA modeling ability over time. At first
376 glance, residual maps tend to be similar to score maps for some dates, which is not surprising
377 because zones with low scores tend to be underestimated while high scores tend to be
378 overestimated by the model. Since the goal is not to perfectly fit the data but to understand the
379 underlying phenomena behind the NDVI, underestimation and overestimation can be seen as
380 complementary information.

381 Compared to the measurements mapped using kriging (Figure 2), the first component's residuals
382 are consistent along the season with CEC and soil variables, showing depression in the middle-
383 west and east of the vineyard. The first component residuals are also consistent with other
384 variables such as soil apparent conductivity and soil organic matter.

385 In vineyard B, the first component's residuals are clearly consistent with vineyard management
386 and clones and, perhaps, with ephemeral water streams, highlighting differences at this period
387 of high vegetative growth and showing differences between the west-east parts of the vineyard.

388 (A)

389 (B)

390 *Figure 10 - Local residuals on both vineyards obtained at different dates during the reconstruction of the NDVI using*
391 *combinations of PCA components: top: PCA 1, middle: PCA 1 + 2, bottom: PCA 1 + 2 + 3.*

392 Regarding the temporal variability, the June image shows high heterogeneity in the first
393 component's residuals; however, this heterogeneity is lower in the July image. This peculiarity
394 was already observed in figure 9 and may explain the substantial adjustment of component 2 in
395 June. As hypothesized previously, it can be explained due to the top pruning performed at the
396 beginning of July, balancing the vegetation cover. Moreover, June being a high vegetative
397 growth period, limiting factors related to soil and its variability may explain observed results.

398 4.5. Comparison between PCA and PLS results

399 The PLS analysis using Pruning Wood Weight as training samples shows that the first
400 component is similar to the one obtained with PCA (results not shown). In vineyard A, the
401 correlation between PCA and PLS first components was $R^2 = 0.99$. However, several
402 differences were observed for the PLS second component, finding that it was highly similar to
403 the first one ($R^2 = 0.85$). This high correlation can be explained by the fact that PLS tries to
404 map the data in a subspace in which latent variables are correlated with explanatory variables,
405 in that case Pruning Wood Weight. Here, a single component is enough to achieve that goal,

406 just like the veraison map was directly linked to Pruning Wood Weight measurements, and any
407 other information is redundant

408 Discussion

409 The f-PCA/f-PLS methods for dimensionality reduction were applied to two vineyard time
410 series to highlight different agronomic spatial phenomena. The f-PCA explained different
411 occurring phenomena such as the stream zones related to supposed ephemeral water streams,
412 soil differences, or differential management of the vineyard.

413 In both vineyards, the first component was quite similar to the information obtained from a
414 classical veraison NDVI map. There is a strong chance that this result will be observed on the
415 majority of vineyards since this first component reflects the primary vigor trend of the vineyard
416 over the whole season. As a result, regarding the first component, the f-PCA does not provide
417 newer information than a NDVI map at veraison (the latter being the final result of growth at
418 the end of the season). However, in both vineyards, the relationship between the pruning wood
419 weight and the f-PCA first component values was higher than with the veraison NDVI maps,
420 suggesting that the first component map computed from the f-PCA methodology accounts better
421 for vine vigor than a single veraison map. One hypothesis could be that vegetation development
422 is the most important source of NDVI variability over the year, and the first component focuses
423 on the main variations within the year, leaving out other and more secondary sources of
424 variation to the other components. By considering the whole time series, f-PCA guarantees that
425 the mapped phenomenon results from the plant vigor dynamic over the whole season.

426 Additional information could be derived from the other components of the f-PCA. Indeed,
427 temporal changes of NDVI cannot be modeled using a single component since each component
428 exhibits variation patterns, especially in high heterogeneity periods such as the vegetation
429 development period. Other components can be considered adjustments of the general trend;
430 however, the information provided by the second and the third components requires agronomic
431 expertise and a particularly good knowledge of field management. It was expected that the first
432 component underfits the original time series, but it is not wished that subsequent components
433 overfit it. Since this phenomenon is difficult to check, keeping only the first three components
434 or even sometimes only the first two is crucial to avoid overfitting data and to create misleading
435 interpretations. The explained variance could be used as an objective metric (e.g., stopping
436 when 95% of the original variance is explained), but visually checking the components and
437 trying to link them with field knowledge should be advised. In addition, each component

438 exhibits variations in different periods of the year. The most noticeable variations were
439 observed in June, related to the complex dynamics within the vineyard.

440 Finally, it is also interesting to note that, while the f-PCA method does not consider spatial
441 autocorrelation (dependencies between neighboring Sentinel-2 pixels), the obtained
442 components naturally show a strong spatial structure, meaning spatial information is not needed
443 in the process.

444 The key findings of this paper can be seen in two ways. The first one is the application of the
445 method: to our knowledge, there is no study using Sentinel-2 temporal data to decompose the
446 vineyard behaviors into several key components. Historically, MODIS satellite images are used
447 to describe seasonal trends on field crops, which were then used for crop classification or
448 forecasting (Carreño-Conde *et al.*, 2021). The coarse resolution of the images made within-field
449 applications in the vineyards impractical, thus they focused only on the temporal variation
450 within several years. The recent Sentinel-2 launches blurred the limits between high spatial
451 resolution imagery and high temporal resolution imagery. Methods like the presented f-PCA
452 can be seen as an appropriate solution to tackle these challenges in a novel way, even though
453 the method is not new. The second one is the knowledge of within-field variability and the
454 increasing importance of satellite imagery in the process (Precision Viticulture). The results
455 support the common observations about within-vineyard variability (Tisseyre *et al.*, 2008) and
456 Sentinel-2 observed variability (Devaux *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, it supports the observation
457 that simplified indicators like NDVI at a single date may struggle to describe several sources
458 of spatial and temporal variability in the vineyard (Hall *et al.*, 2010), thus supporting the need
459 for decomposition algorithms applied to the complete set of Sentinel-2 bands during the season.

460 Conclusions

461 Functional analysis, combined with dimensionality reduction methods (f-PCA, f-PLS), is a
462 promising tool to extract information from NDVI Sentinel-2 time-series of the vine field
463 describing vine growth and vigor. It builds upon the free and open data policy adopted for
464 Sentinel-2 products combined with the rich temporal information of the images. In this work,
465 several key parameters that may support vineyard managers in understanding field variability
466 were linked to a principal component decomposition of the temporal data. The components of
467 the f-PCA were able to explain the vineyard spatial variability better than a single NDVI
468 veraison map since the principal component values had a higher correlation with within-field
469 parameters such as pruning wood weight or yield.

470 Moreover, this paper stressed the need to analyze each component separately, which adds
471 complementary and valuable information, identifying new phenomena that cannot be explained
472 in a veraison map. One key advantage of the method is that only a few components are needed
473 to explain most of the vineyard variability contained in Sentinel-2 time series.

474 The potential for a more granular examination of the f-PCA decomposition at individual dates
475 was also explored. For instance, noticeable component variations were linked to the vineyard's
476 complex dynamics in the vegetation growth period associated with management practices. To
477 our knowledge, this type of approach is quite new in precision agriculture. The methodology
478 proposed here remains a first step to identify the potential of image time series at the within-
479 field scale. It is likely that other methods will be proposed in the near future. It will then be
480 necessary to be able to compare their relevance by proposing, for example, shared reference
481 data to conduct this type of comparison.

482 Further studies may also include the joint use of all Sentinel-2 bands and applying the described
483 methods to larger scales, ranging from groups of vineyards to a whole region. In particular, the
484 spatial structures and patterns emerging from that type of data may be of great interest to better
485 understand regional-scale dynamics.

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